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Research

A Comparison Study between Chinese Woman's Wedding Dress and Bangladeshi Woman's Wedding Dress Saree

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Abstract: Since ancient times, as a national symbol and cultural development, wedding dress plays a very important role in national research. In addition, people can better understand the history of human society and explore the basic laws of the development of human society through a large number of gorgeous wedding dresses. In the development of human society, many wedding dresses have experienced various changes. As a basic model, the "six etiquette" has not changed much in China, and it is still the essential core of marriage customs. In Bangladesh, effective marriage should experience proposal, choose a day and hold a wedding. The most important aspect of marriage is wedding dress. This paper will discuss the different aspects of women's wedding dress in the two countries Chinese woman's wedding costume and Bangladeshi women's wedding dress Saree. Due to different cultural origins, religious concepts and geography, there are different procedures, different clothes, different activities, different colors and different wedding ceremonies between China and Bangladesh. Due to cultural exchanges, China and Bangladesh have some similarities and differences in wedding dress. This article will also discuss some similarities and differences and absorption of wedding culture between China and Bangladesh. By comparing these processes with some related stories, we can easily find the difference. Generally speaking, women's wedding dresses of the two countries give us the impression of romanticism, freedom and fairness.

Keywords: Wedding dress; Style differences; Similarity; Absorption of wedding culture ;Benarasi; LongFengGua; Qipao; Brocade.

Introduction

Chinese used to think that marriage was a way to increase the family's reputation and status. Marriage will add a clan girl, not one's own, so marriage is seen as an important event of the family, not one's own. Love between men and women is not the first condition of marriage. Today, the

concept of marriage in modern society has changed a lot, especially in urban areas, but there are still some differences in some backward areas. In the past, the purpose of their marriage was to increase the family, future generations, protect and enhance the reputation and status of the family, but now the concept has changed. In China and Bangladesh, love and understanding between men and women have become the top priority.

Different from Bangladeshi wedding dress, China has her own special wedding dress. Chinese wedding dress is basically around the theme of auspiciousness and happiness. The mixture of different colors and themes, such as dragon, Phoenix, red and gold, is considered to bring good luck and happiness, and is an indispensable element in Chinese wedding dress and decoration. In addition, other materials of Chinese wedding dress also have strong Chinese characteristics.

In Bangladesh, it has a very colorful wedding occasion, people use Saree and Punjabi, which is designed by various attractive art. Saree is the most beautiful, unique and traditional clothing subcontinent. Saree, traditionally dressed in Bangladeshi style, is the main fashion part of Bangladeshi wedding. In general, the fabric, texture, color and style of a wedding dress may vary depending on the religion and culture of a particular country.

1. THEORY BASIS

Social, Cultural & Religious Origin:

Chinese traditional marriage custom is influenced by the unique clan system. "Three obedience and four virtues" decide that women should become accessories of men and obey family interests. "Orders from their parents, with the help of a matchmaker.". Young people do not have the right to a spouse. It is characterized by a strong feudal political color. Marriage is sometimes a way to make all politics one way. The policy of connecting friendly relations through political marriage is a typical example in history.

The traditional marriage custom is deeply influenced by Confucianism. However, in the Indian subcontinent (Bangladesh, India and Pakistan), marriage practices are deeply influenced by religion and culture and traditions. Of all the religions people seek to worship, Islam (Muslim) is the most influential in Bangladesh. Every step of life in Bangladesh is influenced by this religion, so it has become part of the lifestyle of Bangladesh and has a great impact on clothing.

2. Describing Chinese Women's Wedding Costume:

Different from Bangladeshi wedding dress, China has her own special wedding dress. Chinese wedding dress is basically around the theme of auspiciousness and happiness. The mixture of different colors and themes, such as dragon, Phoenix, red and gold, is considered to bring good luck and happiness, and is an indispensable element in Chinese wedding dress and decoration. In addition, other materials of Chinese wedding dress also have strong Chinese characteristics.

3.1. Colors & Elements of Chinese Wedding Dressing & Decoration Settings

Chinese Wedding Dress:

The main color of Chinese wedding dress is bright red, which is considered to be the most sacred traditional color. You may know that red is the most popular color for Chinese people, because it represents happiness, vitality, life and brilliant happiness in Chinese culture. Red is also used as a symbol of good luck at Chinese weddings to drive away evil spirits. This is different from the west, where the wedding color is mainly pure white and black. The traditional Chinese wedding dress in northern China is usually a dress called Qipao(旗袍) or cheongsam, which is mainly red and embroidered with exquisite gold and silver patterns. Brides in southern China like to wear two-piece clothes, named QunGua or QunKwa(裙褂), because they are often elaborately decorated with golden dragon and Phoenix, so they are usually called longfeng gua(龙凤褂) because Dragon and Phoenix overcoat there.

chinese wedding dress qipao & longfeng gua

3.1.1. Longfenggua (龙凤褂)

These days are very popular among Chinese couples. In China, this is an indispensable Chinese wedding dress. LongfengGua with dragon and Phoenix as the pattern has auspicious significance. In addition to the dragon and Phoenix, five embroidered bats, with the meaning of five blessings, also appear in the dragon and Phoenix melon. Changfenggua is more simplified than the three Chinese wedding dresses mentioned above, which can show the curve shape of women. In modern China, when Chinese newlyweds take Chinese wedding photos, they prefer fengguanxiapei, but when they drink a toast for their guests, they prefer longfenggua.

(Longfeng gua 龙凤褂)

(Chinese wedding dress in Zhou dynasty)

(Chinese wedding dress in Tang Dynasty)

(Chinese wedding dress in Ming Dynasty)

(Chinese wedding color & decoration settings)

3.2. Chinese Wedding Dress in History:

Along the thousands years of long history of ancient China, the style of Chinese wedding dress is different in different dynasties. There were three main Chinese wedding dresses in history China.

3.2.1. Chinese Wedding Dress in Zhou Dynasty (1046BC—256BC):

Zhou Dynasty Chinese wedding dress is characterized by modesty and solemnity. Color is different than in old age. Black and light red are the main colors of the Zhou Dynasty, whereas in later years, the color is bright red. The groom wore a Jubian hat on his head, while the groom wore two layers of clothing, white underwear, black and light red. The bride wore a xunran, including light red underwear and a black coat. In addition, the bride must tie her hair with a 50cm hairband and a 25cm hair clip.

3.2.2. Chinese Clothing during Qin and Han Dynasties(221 B.C.--220 A.D.)

The Qin and Han dynasties (221-A.D.220) saw the unification of the area and character. founded a number of social organizations, including uniforms, to distinguish the hierarchy and social status of the people. China's complete apparel and deck indexes were established in the Han Dynasty

(206-220AD BC). The techniques of yarn dyeing, embroidery and metallic technology developed rapidly during the period, stimulating changes in dress and decoration.

3.2.3. Chinese Clothing during Wei, Jin, South & North Dynasties(220-589)

Chinese apparel the rapid growth of experience in the south, north of the two-generation (220-589). 265 years ago, the culture, beauty and frequent wars of the North and South China merged with them. Many philosophical schools have affected not only the lives of the people but also the design of the garment design.

3.2.4. Chinese Clothing during Tang Dynasty(618-907)

The Chinese wedding dress of the Tang Dynasty absorbed the Zhou Dynasty in the joy of the later years. The groom wore a red dress and the bride in a green dress. Developed at the end of Tang Dynasty on the basis of long-sleeved dressings and flower needles. Clothing is characterized by multi-layered and long sleeves. Japanese kimono was developed from this kind of wedding dress. The bride wears this wedding dress and must be paired with a hair clip made of metal and jewelry. After the Tang Dynasty, the complex Haidian Liv was simplified.

As we all know, the more complex it is, the lower the aesthetic sense. So how does a wedding dress combine such complex art with gorgeous art? The classic of the Tang Dynasty wedding dress is its collar and long sleeves. Tang Dynasty's wedding dress, although matched with a set of hair pins and hair accessories, but never brought a sense of red tape. The bride's green dress was updated with bright red when the season went on.

The Tang Dynasty (618-907) wrote one of the most famous pages in Chinese apparel history. People's clothes are more diverse than ever, because countries are so open to the outside world and people's minds have become international. Women's clothes can be called fashion because they change quickly and are very ostentatious. When a new style is released, many people want to accept it.

3.2.5. Chinese Clothing during Song, Yuan, Ming Dynasties

Casual wear appeared in the Song Dynasty (960-1279), dressed in simple and elegant. During the Yuan Dynasty (1206-1368), mongolians, known as people on horseback, came to power. Their clothing pattern was the blending of Mongolian and Han dynasty's clothing. The clothes are luxurious to the upper classes, but simple and simple in design. The Ming Dynasty (1368-1644) changed dramatically. Clothing design has emerged a new concept, without limiting a style, advocating natural beauty, for the clothing culture to bring vitality and vitality. From the Ming

Dynasty to modern China, taking the wife is a small civil test for Chinese men, so the groom's wedding dress is the clothing of nine-level officer (九品官服, Chinese pinyin: jiu pin guan fu), and the ranking of phoenix corsets and robes (凤冠霞帔, Chinese pinyin: feng guan xiapei) is the bride. Among all the wedding dress styles in ancient time, Fengguan was treated as mostly admirable ornament of woman. FengguanXiapei was being considered as the main wedding dress since the Ming Dynasty.

3.2.6. Chinese Clothing during Qing Dynasty:

In the Qing Dynasty (1644-1911) garments were transformed into a neat, stable, and shiny form. During the 200 years of the Qing Empire, the world experienced dramatic changes, such as the Italian Renaissance and the discovery of Columbus America, but these changes did not affect traditional Chinese clothing because of China's closed policy. People still wear clothes that show grades and lifestyle. Retreating from the outside culture has left a precious legacy on traditional Chinese clothing.

3.2.7. Chinese Clothing from 1930s till Modern Era

From the 1930s to the present, Chinese clothing began to catch on. In the 1930s and 1940s, the dress was further westernized and custom-made into a flat body. In the 1940s and 1960s, cheongsams were worn daily in Hong Kong until the late 1960s. Today, many Chinese brides choose modern-style Qipao or Longfeng Kwa (traditional Chinese dress similar to Qipao) as traditional wedding dresses.

The wedding dress won't end there. Chinese brides can wear red silk veils to help cover their blushes! We like the idea because we imagine nerves! It is also a vow, and when the groom takes off the veil, it marks the beginning of a lifetime of cherishing each other.

Chinese brides can also choose a more shiny headpiece, China Phoenix Colong. The corset is perhaps the most respectable ornament, and although it originated in the Ming Dynasty, it resonates with modern brides with its exquisite craftsmanship. Chinese brides do not omit bridal shoes - they will see red or pink hues and subtle patterns.

3.3. Materials Included Traditional Chinese Wedding dress:

Covering Veil:	Chinese Phoenix Coronets:
(Chinese phoenix coronet and ROBE OF RANK for queen in Ming dynasty)	(Chinese wedding shoes)

3.3.1. Covering Veil:

The Chinese bride's veil is a square piece of red silk, usually embroidered with a design of peony or phoenix pattern. The significance behind this tradition is that people believe that the red covered veil can drive away those impolite things and also cover up the vicious washing of the bride's face. In traditional Chinese weddings, the bride is handed over by the bridegroom. Her head should be covered with a red veil, and the whole ceremony falls on her shoulders. The veil will not fall off until all relatives and friends leave. The bridegroom was lucky to take off her veil. Traditionally, the bridegroom should use a small steel yard to remove the veil; this means that the bridegroom can make his bride listen to him voluntarily. Imagine the bridegroom taking off his veil and seeing

a red and excited face, sitting on the edge of the new bed in the timid candlelight. This is a special and sweet moment. A bride in a veil is associated with a special occasion in which lovers desire to live.

Chinese Phoenix Coronets:

Chinese Phoenix Coronet——凤冠 , That is to say, China means Phoenix crown, which is the most respectable decoration of ancient women. Since the Ming Dynasty, Phoenix brassiere has been an important part of Chinese wedding dress. This wedding dress is considered to be the most classic and representative of all Chinese wedding dresses. Although suits and black suits are very popular in China today, many couples will choose to wear traditional Chinese wedding dresses as the second set of clothes to complete the wedding ceremony. In addition to tradition, the delicate beauty of the Phoenix crown is the main reason to attract brides to wear it, which is the most beautiful and glorious moment in their life.

3.3.2. Traditional Chinese Wedding Shoes:

At a wedding, the bride usually wears a special pair of wedding shoes. Traditionally, in the south of Fujian Province, the bride has to wear a pair of shoes embroidered with turtle or deer patterns, which symbolizes the blessing, happiness and longevity after marriage. In southern Zhejiang Province, brides have to wear a pair of shoes called Shang jiaoxie (shoes worn when stepping into a car seat) to pray for good luck. Brides or others can make wedding shoes. These shoes are made of red and green cloth, usually with soft soles. These shoes should be worn by the bride when she is going to step into the car chair. In some places, relatives who make the shoes for the bride get lucky, while in others, the bride and another single girl make them on the morning of the wedding day.

4. Describing Bangladeshi Women's Wedding Costume:

In Bangladesh, we have a very colorful wedding occasion, we use Saree and Punjabi, which is designed by various attractive art. Saree is the most beautiful, unique and traditional clothing subcontinent. Saree, traditionally dressed in Bangladeshi style, is the main fashion part of Bangladeshi wedding. In general, the fabric, texture, color and style of a wedding dress may vary depending on the religion and culture of a particular country.

Wedding dress is an important part of fashion. It is an important part of fashion industry. Every dress has its own custom. A wedding dress is a dress worn by a bride or bridegroom at a wedding.

4.1.Colors & Elements of Bengali women’s Wedding Dressing & Decoration Settings:

Bangladeshi Women’s wedding Costume

4.1.1. Saree:

Saree is the most beautiful, unique and traditional clothing subcontinent. Saree, traditionally dressed in Bangladeshi style, is the main fashion part of Bangladeshi wedding. In general, the fabric, texture, color and style of a wedding dress may vary depending on the religion and culture of a particular country. Nowadays, modern women like Shari made of various fabrics and designs. Shari, which is commonly used by women, is discussed below.

4.2. TYPES OF BANGLADESHI SAREE: Today there are mainly four varieties of Banarasi saree available.

4.2.1. Dhakai Banarasi: The Bridal Masterpiece

On the wedding day in Bangladesh, most brides wear Banarasi Sarees, which are basically red. In Bangladesh, women can't think of a wedding with Saree, especially Banarasi and the border of 'decorative gold embellishment' and 'zari' as its name. The history of Banarasi saree can be traced back to the Mughal rule in the 16th century, which originated in the northern Indian city of Banaras. In Bangladesh, Muslims who migrated from banaras began to make banarasi in Muhammadpur and Mirpur of Dhaka in 1950. According to the source of the Bangladesh Handloom board, this tradition is still handed down from generation to generation.

Benarasi's charm has not even diminished. The largest hub of Dhaka Benarasi Saree markets is located in Mipur. This place is called benrasi Palli and may be one of the largest Saree markets in the world.

Dhakai Benarasi Saree-the Bridal Masterpiece

Benarasi Saree is the bride's first choice for two reasons. The first is the heritage of Saree, a special breed in Bangladeshi saree holds. The second is the dazzling color and the characteristics of Benarasi. Every girl wants to look gorgeous on her wedding, and a Benarasi can definitely do that.

Today there are mainly **four** varieties of Banarasi saree available. Those are

- **Pure Silk (Katan);**
- **Shattir,**
- **Organza that is fine kora with zari and silk works and**
- **The Georgette.**

4.2.2. BROCADE WORK IN BENARASI:

Brocade is a textile that has a conventional weave in which the pile is usually crossed by warping. In general, when the gold and silver thread and the textile thread are densely woven, the special thread can omit the channel of the standard wet channel on a certain amount of warped thread according to the mode, and regularly omit it through the set mode type. The heddles so arranged, on different occasions, elevate and depress asymmetrical threads in turn, as required in the pattern.

The most striking feature of this model is that it is made of gold, silver and silk. The main pattern of this pattern is a flower or a bunch of flowers. A slightly smaller and mottled bouquet spreads throughout the base. Nature is the main source of design, flower form is called butis or butas. Butis (Figure 2.5) are smaller and are usually made of a flower, bird, animal, or leaf.

There are basic patterns which are shaped into several forms such as Badam (Almond) buti, Kairi (Mango) buti, Chaand (Moon) buti, Asharfi (coin) buti (Fig. 2.6), Paan (beetle leaf) buti and Pankha (fan) buti. There are a number of patterns which are derived from jewellery.

4.2.3. Karchupi-

Karchupi is a special complex thread work that is used to make dresses

Materials are more attractive. It's a process of embedding puthi, zari and other decorations

The material is as sharp as a fishhook through a special needle.

Other Bangladeshi local sarees are:

- ❖ Jamdani: The Most Local Bangladeshi Saree
- ❖ Silk Saree: Rajshahi's Pride
- ❖ Tangail Handloom Saree
- ❖ Katan Saree: Affordable, Yet Top-Notch

As we already know, Bangladesh, India and Pakistan were the same country before the partition in 1947, so most of the cultures and customs of the three religious destinations were almost the same. Saree is used as the main dress for wedding brides in all three countries.

Choose and wear Sarees according to different seasons and functions. Sarees types include silk, Georgette, bride and Wedding Sarees, etc. Sarees has been the dominant at the wedding in Bangladesh

4.3.Draping of Saree:

5. Bengali Bridal Jewelry (Goyna) types:

Bangladeshi brides usually wear a lot of jewelry, mostly gold and silver jewelry, sometimes clothing jewelry. In the past few years, women often wear a lot of gold at weddings, but as time goes on, most women now wear the right amount of gold. Indian subcontinent brides, especially Bangladeshi brides, will see wearing traditional or modern jewelry in 99.99 cases. Here are the most used jewelry by Bangladeshi women during weddings. The most commonly used Bangladeshi wedding jewelry is as follows.

- ❖ Bengali Bride ‘Sonar Mukut’ / Golden Crown Wedding Bridal Jewelry
- ❖ Bengali Bride Headgear / Tikli
- ❖ hair Bun Pin/ Brooch
- ❖ Nose Ring or Nath
- ❖ Kaan er Dul or Earrings for Bengali Brides
- ❖ Kaan er Dul with Golden Kaan Shape – Ear Shaped Earring
- ❖ Kanpasha or Large Golden Studs
- ❖ The Chick or Choker Necklace
- ❖ Panch Noli Har or Sat Noli Har – Necklace
- ❖ Sonar Haar / Golden Haar
- ❖ Sonar haar(Gold Necklace) with Tassles
- ❖ Ratanchoor or Hathphool or Hand Harness
- ❖ Finger Rings or Angti for the Bride
- ❖ Mantasha or Gold Wristlet Designs
- ❖ Baala or Bangle
- ❖ Chur
- ❖ Churi/ Chudi- Thin Gold Bangles
- ❖ Ananta-Armllet:
- ❖ Kamarbandh- Waist-Chain
- ❖ Silver Payal/ Payel Anklet
- ❖ Bengali style Shoes(Matching with Saree)

<p align="center">Bengali Bride Headgear / Tikli:</p>	<p align="center">Nose Ring or Nath:</p>

Bengali Bride 'Sonar Mukut' / Golden Crown

Kaan er Dul or Earrings

Kaan er Dul with Golden Kaan Shape – Ear Shaped Earring

Hair Bun Pin/ Brooch:

Kanpasha or Large Golden Studs

The Chick or Choker Necklace

Panch Noli Har or Sat Noli Har – Necklace

Sonar Haar / Golden Haar:

Sonar haar(Gold Necklace) with Tassles

Ratanchoor or Hathphool or Hand Harness

Mantasha or Gold Wristlet Designs

Finger Rings or Angti

Mantasha or Gold Wristlet Designs

Baala or Bangle

Chur:

Churi/ Chudi- Thin Gold Bangles:

Kamarbandh- Waist-Chain:

Silver Payal/ Payel Anklet:

6. Conclusion:

As marriage and family are social systems, marriage is formed through the long-term historical evolution of marriage customs, which has a great impact on the pattern of marriage clothing. In the development of human history and socialism, marriage system and family system have experienced different development processes. In family formation, weddings must be followed as a standardized procedure. Wedding dress shows the norms, casting and social status of the specific country. The wedding includes not only the wedding, but also the preparation and performance stages of the wedding, including the wedding dress, color, other materials worn by the bride and groom and other celebrations. It runs through the whole life process. As a symbol of the country and a symbol of cultural development, wedding dress plays an important role. It plays a very important role in Ethnic Studies and the historical development of a particular society. The difference of wedding dress between China and Bangladesh is inevitable. Different religions, cultural origins, marriage concepts and regions have resulted in different wedding dresses in the two countries. This highly represents the personalities of the two countries.

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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